

British Institute of Persian Studies

P.O. box 2617,

Teheran,

Iran.

26/5/1970.

Dear Mr. Gueritz,

I enclose a copy of an application to renew my current Fellowship of the British Institute of Persian Studies for the year 1970-1971. This consists of:

Curriculum vitae.

Progress of research.

Explanation of research.

Projected research.

Prior financial support.

Details of funds requested.

You will notice that although this is primarily an application to the major Fellowship Fund I intend to spend some time at Siraf so that this part of the Fund is also concerned.

Seven duplicate copies of this application are being sent under separate cover.

I must again apologize for leaving this application to the very last minute.

Yours sincerely,

Andrew Williamson.

PREVIOUS FINANCIAL SUPPORT1967-1968:

The Department of Education and Science-
 for travel and living expenses. . . . £ 780

£ 780

1968-1969:

The Department of Education and Science-
 for travel and living expenses. . . .c. £ 1,150

The Sirāf Fellowship Fund of The British
 Institute of Persian Studies-
 for work at Sirāf £ 200

The British Institute of Persian Studies-
 for the purchase of a Land Rover. . . . £ 400

£ 1,750

1969-1970:

The Department of Education and Science-
 for travel and living expenses. . . .c. £ 1,200

The British Institute of Persian Studies-
 for the purchase of a motorbicycle
 and research expenses £ 450

£ 1,650

PROJECTED RESEARCH

1) JUNE 1970 to SEPTEMBER 1970:

Preparation of a report on the excavations at Sīrjān, and completion of the historical section of my research on the items of trade.

2) OCTOBER 1970 to MARCH 1971:

Completion of archaeological survey of Islamic sites in Southern Iran (begun 1968-1969) along the following routes:

- a) The Persian Gulf coast from Qālāt to the border of Khūzistān.
- b) The remaining Persian islands in the Gulf: Qeshm, Lārak, Henjām, Henderābi, Lāvān, and Khārg.
- c) The valleys behind the coast between Sīrāf and Lar.
- d) The routes from Bandar Abbās to Sīrjān and Bam.

I intend to spend two months assisting on the excavations at Sīrāf, and the remainder of the period of the excavation continuing survey in the area.

3) APRIL 1971 to OCTOBER 1971:

Final preparation of results in Oxford.

PROGRESS OF RESEARCH

AUGUST 1967 to MARCH 1968:

Participation in Iran on archaeological excavations at Nush-i-Jan and Sīrāf, and on the study of the finds enabled me to gain additional archaeological experience and a considerable background in Islamic archaeology.

APRIL 1968 to AUGUST 1968:

A preliminary study of the documentary material was carried out at Oxford.

AUGUST 1968 to APRIL 1969:

Survey in Southern Iran as well as subsidiary study in Teheran was undertaken. The survey comprised an intensive investigation of the area and routes from Istakhr and Shirāz to Sīrjān and Bam, a reconnaissance of Persian Seistan, and a study of Islamic sites discovered by Mr. W. M. Sumner in the Kur River plain North of Shirāz. The Persian Gulf coast was investigated from Jāsk to Qālāt, and the islands of Kish and Hormuz were briefly visited.

MAY 1969 to JULY 1969:

Further research was carried out at Oxford on documentary materials.

AUGUST 1969 to APRIL 1970:

Delays in obtaining my permit for renewed survey as well as that for excavation at the site of Sīrjān (discovered in 1968), a series of illnesses, and a fall from my motorbicycle have permitted only seventeen days of survey in the Bushehr Peninsula, near Sīrāf, and in the region of Bandar Abbās.

APRIL 1970 to MAY 1970:

Excavations were undertaken at Sīrjān, financed by the Stein-Arnold Fund of The British Academy, The British Institute of Persian Studies, and the Mayerstein Fund of Oxford University.

EXPLANATION OF RESEARCH

My research project is entitled: "Archaeological and documentary material for the history and mechanisms of commerce in Southern Iran from the seventh century to the end of the Portuguese Period."

The commercial importance of the area in historic times, until the development of the route to the East around the Cape of Good Hope, is well documented. A succession of major port sites on the North shore of the Persian Gulf, such as Siraf, Kish, and Hormuz, played a major role in the transshipment and distribution of Far Eastern and Indian spices and other commodities to the Middle East and Europe, as well as participating in Indian Ocean and local commerce. These ports ranked amongst the richest in the world, but the reasons for their size and for the rise and decline of each in succession have not as yet been adequately explained.

The archaeological field work for this research consists of an intensive survey of the area bordering the North coast of the Persian Gulf and including the Iranian islands in the Gulf. Thanks to grants over the last two years from The British Institute of Persian Studies, I am equipped with a Land Rover and a motorbicycle to aid in the efficient coverage of the tracks in this difficult country. All sites investigated are recorded in terms of location, dimension, character of habitation, and resources, and a large sample of artefacts is collected from the surface. Almost 700 sites of all periods have been so far examined in this manner. After study the material from these will be deposited in the excavation museum at Siraf.

Standing monuments, and especially all inscriptions, are being fully recorded. The prehistoric pottery is being studied by Miss Martha Prickett of Harvard University and Mr. W. M. Sumner of the University of Pennsylvania.

The Southern part of Iran, and more particularly the coastal areas of the Persian Gulf and the islands, are specially suited for the type of intensive survey I am undertaking. Since the area is impoverished today, present settlement is small and rarely masks older material. Natural disasters and constant insecurity have necessitated the frequent abandonment of village and city sites. In addition, movement has been facilitated because settlement has been possible even in waterless areas by the use of cisterns to collect storm water run off.

The ceramic, glass, and other archaeological materials which are collected in this survey can now be dated fairly closely by reference to the artefacts recovered from the stratigraphic excavations at Siraf. This permits the mapping of location and concentration of settlement during eight well defined periods. In addition, maps are being prepared to show the trade of pottery from its place of manufacture. The excavations on the kilns at Siraf have clearly demonstrated that certain types of characteristic pottery were produced on this site. The excavations recently completed at Sirjan have conclusively identified the large range of fine pottery produced in its kilns. In addition, in the last two years eleven separate kiln sites have been located in different regions. The distribution from these kilns gives an illuminating picture of the local trade in ceramics. The direction of long distance trade is demonstrated in the distribution of

pottery, glass, and porcelains identified as originating in Mesopotamia, the Levant, or the Far East. An attempt is also being made to identify the sources of the steatite found in abundance on many sites. Through mapping the distribution of oyster middens and by examining intermingled or associated pottery and glass, the location and extent of this industry is being illustrated at different periods.

This archaeological work is by no means a substitute for documentary research. By studying the works of the Islamic geographers and travellers, and those from China and Europe, as well as the Portuguese papers of the colonial period, an understanding of the perishable commodities of trade, of the importance of individual towns, and of the routes taken between them is emerging. However, the archaeological material is most significant in that it provides a quantitative assessment of the size of sites, of the directions of trade, and of the relative importance of different routes, none of which are more than hinted at in the frequently contradictory historical record. By combining archaeological and historical material, a picture is being produced of the economic and political mechanisms of mediaeval trade in this commercially important area.

The archaeological material gathered so far indicates a striking concentration of coastal settlement by period. For example, preliminary survey indicates that within 50 kms. of Siraf there is a string of large and contemporaneous sites occupying in total more than three times the area of the major site. However, occupation has been very much reduced in this region at all later periods. The Bushehr Peninsula too, has many Sassanian

and very early Islamic sites, three of which measure over 1 km. square. Yet the area seems to have rapidly sunk from this great prosperity, since there is very little settlement between the 9th and 15th centuries A.D.. This would seem to suggest that the records of families migrating from one city to another as the trade centres shifted might represent a major movement in population.

In investigating the historically attested trade routes, it has been found that on the Iranian plateau virtually no pottery or glass was traded along the Shiraz-Sirjan-Bam route which figures so prominently in the Islamic geographers' accounts of the overland route to Seistan and the Indus. These three cities are contained in separate, scarcely overlapping areas within which fine pottery was distributed from kilns situated near Istakhr, at Sirjan, and at an unknown site near Bam or in Persian Seistan. On the coast however, long distance trade in large quantities of pottery is attested. Even items of such low value as the domestic coarse ware from the Siraf kilns were traded to Minab, 500 kms. down the coast, while storage jars reached as far as East Africa. In the mediaeval period glazed pottery from Mesopotamia was traded in large quantities throughout the Persian Gulf and adjacent areas, yet little reached the Iranian plateau. Similarly, since the coming of Islam Far Eastern pottery and porcelain are found in large quantities in the warm lands around the Persian Gulf. However, until the 14th century A.D. very little penetrated further inland. The city sites of Sirjan, Kirman, and Istakhr are the only mounds on the southern plateau with Far Eastern pottery antedating the 14th century A.D.. Instead, the Chinese ceramics found in such quantities at Siraf and Kish were shipped to Mesopotamia. From the 14th century A.D. there is a

significant change in the pattern, and 42 sites on the southern plateau have been recorded with 14th to 16th century A.D. celadon or blue and white. By this period it seems that the economic hinterland of the major Persian ports was shifting from Mesopotamia and the West to the Iranian plateau.

My extensive discoveries of oyster middens, frequently mixed with Islamic pottery from the earliest period onwards and associated with sites even on the most barren parts of the coast, indicate the considerable economic importance of this industry. Although they are scarcely mentioned by the Islamic sources, pearl exports to the East are cited in foreign accounts, both Chinese and European. These accounts also stress the importance of the export of horses from the Persian Gulf to India, and suggest the possibility that the ports of the Persian Gulf (of which those on the northern shore were always the most important) to some extent traded their own products to the East, rather than merely acting as trans-shipment and distribution points, as has hitherto been assumed. In this way the Persian Gulf, together with East Africa, played some part in actually generating and financing the spice trade. To be specific, pearls and horses from the Persian Gulf, and ivory from East Africa, which were in demand in India and the Far East, were traded for oriental products and spices. The manufactured goods which the inhabitants of the Persian Gulf lacked, such as pottery and glass, were to some extent supplied from Mesopotamia and the West in return for the spices obtained from the sale of Persian Gulf products further East. Since these Western and Levantine products were in little demand in the spice producing East, the direct shipping of spices to the Levant was, as the Egyptian Geniza records show,

mainly financed by the export of precious metals. However, by medium of the indirect trade through the Persian Gulf, spices could flow Westward, financed by the export of manufactured goods to the Gulf area. This does, I believe, make some contribution to the problem which has vexed so many scholars, of how the spice trade was financed without a considerable drain of precious metals from the Mediterranean and Arab world.